

1 **STK36 addiction in the circulating tumor cell reveals developmental dynamics of kinase**
2 **addiction in the circulating tumor cell.**

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8 Addiction to *STK36* was observed in the circulating tumor cell in men with castration resistant prostate
9 cancer and in women with stage IV metastatic breast cancer. This accompanied similarly conserved,
10 recently described addictions to STK kinases *STK31* and *STK39* in CTCs isolated from the peripheral
11 blood of humans with breast cancer and prostate cancer. The circulating tumor cell transcriptome reveals
12 a conserved developmental trajectory in a key stage of the cancer life cycle wherein the developmental
13 process instructs the signaling addiction, here manifested by a specific STK kinase fingerprint.
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